

TYPES OF RUNNING EXERCISES AND THEIR METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes in detail the characteristics of the development of children of primary and preschool age, the basics of education and training, teaching physical education exercises, especially running exercises, introducing them to the rules of correct running.

Currently, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, extensive work is being carried out in our country to improve the management system in the field of physical education and sports, to develop mass sports, to select and educate talented sportsmen, and to strengthen the field with qualified personnel. Scientifically based modern systems, forms and methods of physical education of children have been introduced in our republic, and important tasks have been defined in this field. For the implementation of such tasks, the ground has been created for the development of the field of special physical education, the development of rules for teaching children of preschool age the running exercise, which is the basis of physical exercise, among other areas.

Running is a cyclical type of movement. Like walking, it is characterized by the repetition of cycles performed by changing the support positions on the surface, alternately moving the legs

forward, and harmony of the movements of the hands. However, running is significantly different from walking. During running, the flight phase occurs when both feet of the runner are off the ground. The flight situation increases the person's running speed. It lengthens its stride, allowing it to move forward with the muscles relaxed under the influence of inertia. Due to the inhibition of the activity of the nerve centers, they ensure the recovery of the work capacity, as well as the entire neuromuscular system.

Exercises for transitioning to running are aimed at creating light, fast, free movement with coordinated movement of legs and arms. The process of walking involves alternating contraction and relaxation of a large number of muscle groups. During running, energy expenditure increases, therefore, the volume of breathing, blood circulation, gas exchange rate increases. Running at the right time helps to general physical development, improvement of the function

of the central nervous system, training of the cardiovascular and respiratory system.

Fast, active running should end with a gradual decrease in physical load - the step will be slowed down, which will help the pulse to return to normal. A sudden transition from a fast movement to a static position (standing or sitting) can create an unpleasant situation for an untrained cardiovascular system, which should be taken into account when working with children. Running is formed when the child reaches the age of two and reaches its perfection by the age of three. The running of a 2.5-3-year-old child is characterized by small steps. Many children struggle to get up and run with their feet fully pressed. At this age, children prefer to run than walk. When they first learn the skill of running, they run with uneven, difficult steps and do not follow the direction well. As a result of training, the signs of correct running are strengthened: in the flight position, the body is slightly bent forward, the head is raised, the arms are bent at the elbows, and the movements of the arms and legs are coordinated.

When the child reaches the age of 4, the coordination of the movements of the arms and legs during running is improved under the influence of training, and the flight rhythm improves. However, the length of the step is still not enough, so the children are given exercises for running in lines, circles, turning and catching when running fast.

By the time a child reaches the age of five, he has mastered the technique of running, although he has not yet reached the level of exact performance in its details. In training to run, attention is paid to improving details, making running light and fast.

Children learn age-appropriate running techniques by the time they reach the age of six. They manage to follow the directions with light rhythm, enthusiasm, coordination of movements, flight. In training, the main focus is on improving running, increasing its speed (covering a 30-meter distance in 7.5-6.5 minutes by the end of the year). Children practice various tasks by running.

In order to improve the quality of running in children, as in walking, it is advisable to use the following different types of running: running on tiptoe, running with a big step, running with high hips that train the muscles of the abdominal wall, back and surface of the legs; rhythmic running to music that affects coordination and ease of movement; running with tasks performed on the basis of signals, running around objects and with objects (rope, belt); 87 overcoming obstacles, running on a limited surface (drawn border), shuttle running, which helps to acquire spatial aim and coordination of movements; running to each other; left hand and hook and spread run. This type of running serves as a good exercise for spatial and collective targeting, develops agility and responsiveness to changes in the environment.

The educational value of running exercises is to help children acquire various useful goals.

Running is carried out in accordance with the plan of training at different speeds in physical education classes: fast running (2-3 times for 20 meters, with a break), which trains the quickness of speed-strength qualities and increases the functional capabilities of children; Running (2-4 times) alternating with walking (at moderate speed) for 80-120 meters. It

helps build general endurance: jogging 400 meters slowly over uneven terrain is also

an important tool for building general endurance.

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